

1 **BK virus is latent in man and has oncogenic functions.**

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7 We measured whole transcription by RNA-sequencing in primary human renal epithelial cells, cells of the
8 kidney, following infection with the BK polyomavirus. We demonstrate here directly oncogenic potential of
9 BK polyomavirus infection. Infection of primary renal epithelial cells with BK virus resulted in activation of
10 master oncogenic homeobox TCF19 and FEN1 within three days post-infection in vitro. BK virus is latent
11 in man and has obvious oncogenic potential.

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